

LEGAL REGULATION OF REGIONAL COOPERATION ON TOURISM IN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE ORGANIZATION OF TURKIC STATES

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Abstract. *One of the most notable regional organizations – the Organization of Turkic States, in which Uzbekistan participates as an equal member, focuses on the development of cooperation in the field of tourism among other spheres. In this study, the author noticed and analysed the several agreements on tourism that were signed in the framework of OTS and continue expanding till now. Furthermore, conclusions and proposals were developed on signing special treaties for tourism development in this organization.*

Keywords: *agreement, OTS (Organization of Turkic States), tourism, cooperation, Uzbekistan.*

Аннотация. *Одна из наиболее важных региональных организаций – Организация Тюркских Государств, в которой Узбекистан участвует на правах равноправного участника, уделяет особое внимание развитию сотрудничества в сфере туризма среди других сфер. В данном исследовании автор проанализировала несколько соглашений по туризму, которые были подписаны в рамках ОТГ и продолжают расширяться до сих пор. Кроме того, были разработаны выводы и предложения по заключению в этой организации специальных договоров по развитию туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *соглашение, ОТГ (Организация Тюркских Государств), туризм, сотрудничество, Узбекистан.*

Annotatsiya. *O‘zbekiston teng huquqli a‘zo sifatida ishtirok etayotgan muhim mintaqaviy tashkilotlardan biri – Turkiy davlatlar tashkiloti boshqa sohalar qatorida turizm sohasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratmoqda. Muallif tomonidan ushbu tadqiqotida TDT doirasida imzolangan va hozirgacha kengayib borayotgan turizm bo‘yicha bir qancha shartnomalarni ko‘rib chiqilgan holda tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur tashkilotda turizmni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha maxsus shartnomalar imzolash bo‘yicha xulosa va takliflar ishlab chiqildi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *shartnoma, TDT (Turkiy davlatlar tashkiloti), turizm, hamkorlik, O‘zbekiston.*

The origins of each development of cooperation begin with maintaining a contractual-legal basis between the parties of this collaboration and partnership. A similar practice is implemented in the sphere of tourism. The integral role of regional organizations should be underlined to develop cooperation in this sphere.

The Acapulco document on tourism reaffirmed once again that “world tourism can be a vital force for world peace and can provide the moral and intellectual basis for international understanding and interdependence among nations” and “can contribute to the establishment of a new international economic order that will help to eliminate the economic gap between developed and developing countries”. Hence, considering the integral role of tourism in maintaining peace and its integrative function among states, it should be emphasized that, the integration of states for

developing tourism would possess an important place in growing their economy, promoting peaceful relations between countries, and sustainable development of the world society.

International regional organizations play an important role in maintaining collaboration and partnership among states. Therefore, the international-legal cooperation of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism is constructed through both bilateral and multilateral contractual bases. The most notable regional organizations as the OTS (Organization of Turkic States), in which Uzbekistan participates as an equal member, among other issues pay attention to developing cooperation in the sphere of tourism.

OTS serves as a vital platform for fostering economic, cultural, and security cooperation among its member states [3, 130].

Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan “About measures for providing expeditious development of tourist industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan” emphasizes the expansion of international cooperation in the field of tourism [4,2]. Also, in the Conception of foreign-policy activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it marks that one of the priority directions of the foreign policy of Uzbekistan is considered to be the further development of relationships with the neighbouring, with which our country is linked with historically formed political, economic, transport-communication and other connections. Uzbekistan considers the Organization to be an effective mechanism of regional cooperation with great unrealized opportunities and unifying potential.

Uzbekistan has been actively participating in the Organization of Turkic States. In particular, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward more than 35 specific and important initiatives aimed at further development of multilateral cooperation within this organization. To date, more than 20 of these initiatives have been implemented [2]. Precisely, In 2022, Qoqand was announced as the "Tourist Capital of the Turkic World", The project "Tabarruk Ziyarat" was launched and the "road map" on Tourism.

The legal framework of cooperation between OTS member states in the field of tourism begins its origin from 2014. It is considered that the tourism potential of the Member States has a privileged place in the multidimensional and in-depth cooperation process created within the framework of OTS. To this end, 8 Ministerial and 18 Working Group Meetings were held since the establishment [7].

First meetings were dedicated to organizations' questions, in particular, the 4th Organization of Turkic States Summit, which was held in Bodrum in 2014 and dedicated to “Tourism Cooperation”. Following the Bodrum Summit, the efforts mainly focused on the transformation of the historical Silk Road into an attractive tourist destination. The Summit in 2014 placed a significant emphasis on boosting the tourism sector, aiming to facilitate tourism exchanges and revenue generation among Turkic nations [1].

The outcome of the Ministerial Meeting of the 6th Meeting of the Ministers in Charge of Tourism of the Organization of Turkic States in 2021 in Kokand was to launch the “Turkic World Tourism Capital” project to promote tourism in the region, in which one of the cities from the Member States will be designated as “Turkic World Tourism Capital” annually.

It is very important for the citizens of the member countries of the Organization to get to know each other and the historical and cultural riches of other member countries through tourism. In order to share the unique values of the Turkic world with the whole world, the members of the alliance must know and understand their own values. The Modern Silk Road project, organized in line with this common purpose, will be valid for Türkiye located on the tourism route [5, 158].

The first regulation on tourism was adopted in the 7th Meeting of the Ministers in Charge of Tourism of the Organization of Turkic States on 23-24 May 2022 in Shamakhi, Azerbaijan. As the outcomes of the Ministerial Meeting, the Parties adopted the regulation on the “Turkic World Tourism Capital”, which presents the general framework for the said program, and agreed that Shamakhi will be the Turkic World Tourism Capital for the year 2023.

It should be emphasized that, at the organizational level questions on tourism are discussed and initiatives have been implemented after almost every meeting. However, in terms of contractual legal regulation, in comparison with other regional organizations, these relations should be documented. For instance, tourism issues are mentioned in the Declaration “On humanitarian cooperation of states - participants of the CIS”, and which was signed in August 2005 for the realization of this Declaration, which was called the Agreement “On humanitarian cooperation of states - participants of the CIS”. According to the provisions of these documents, the country intends to guarantee the achievement of specific objectives in the fields of culture, science, education, information, sport, and tourism [6].

With this regard, in conclusion, it should be underlined following proposals:

- To sign of a tourism cooperation agreement between the member states of the OTS with establishing an institutional body - the Tourism Council, which acts as the main one for tourism development in the framework of OTS.

- To create of the Union of the Association of Tour Operators of the OTS member States. It will increase competition among the tourist companies of member states, which can cause further development of the tourism sector. This cooperation helps to construct “close” relationships between the nongovernmental tourism sector of member states. It would help to develop face-to-face dialogue of tour operators and competition between them would lead to progress and cooperation of tour operators soon.

- It is also advisable, to pay more attention to different types of tourism, such as youth tourism, child, family and agro, and ecotourism between member states in the framework of OTS. Surely, legal basis in the form of agreements, memorandum of understanding, and/or programs are required to elaborate for implementing the above-mentioned initiatives.

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